

MELAMINE-MELTBLOWN NONWOVEN A HIGH-PERFORMANCE MATERIAL COMBINING FOR THE FIRST TIME THERMOSET MELAMINE WITH EXCELLENT THERMAL AND ACOUSTIC PROPERTIES

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INTRODUCTION:

A novel approach to combine the thermoplastic processability with thermoset type polymer properties was met, enabling the production of an innovative fabric, nonwoven material with superior properties commercially called smartMELAMINE. smartMELAMINE is a modified melamine (Figure 1.) material¹ that has a thermoplastic processing window which makes it applicable in conventional thermoplastic processes such as extrusion and meltblown.

Figure 1: 1, 3, 5 - Triazine - 2, 4, 6-triamine (melamine).

Table 1: Properties of fibers.

Characteristics	Fibers smartMELAMINE®
Color	white, light amber (treated) or colored e.g. with carbon black
Texture nonwoven	Paper-like, wadding-like, foam-like, rollable, stackable → consistency and surfaces are largely customizable .
Weight [g/m ² ,gsm]	30 – 600
Density [kg/m ³]	10 – 60
Thickness [mm]	up to 30
Fineness [µm]	1 - 25
Width [m]	2.4
Made-up	rolled, stacked
Chemical resistant	yes
UV resistant	yes

Figure 2: Scanning electron microscope (SEM, ZEISS Sigma VP).

FLAME RETARDENCY

- smartMELAMINE heat dimensional stability → non burn, shrink, melt or drip.
- Shape → No change with high temperature.
- Inherent flame resistance → LOI 32%.
- Emissions → very low (ÖkoTex 100 Class 1, VDA 275).
- Smoke gas → low, non toxic (EN 45545).
- Maximum use temperature → up to 350°C.
- Continuous use temperature → up to 240°C.
- Thermal decomposition → ~400°C.

Figure 3: Flammability test (Vertical burn test) of smartMELAMINE.

INSULATION

- Acoustic insulation
 - Excellent properties.
 - Half weight of smartMELAMINE → same/better results (Figure 4).
- Thermal insulation
 - Superior thermal insulation properties.
 - Thermal conductivity as a standalone nonwoven is 0,028 W/mK (DIN 52612).
- Vacuum insulation
 - Thermal conductivity of VIP's with smartMELAMINE® → 0,002 W/mK.

Figure 4 : Tested sound absorption coefficient (α) in depen of frequency (DIN EN ISO 10534-2).

Figure 5: Vacuum insulation panels.

CONCLUSION

- Advantages of smartMELAMINE: flame retardancy, thermal resistance, acoustic insulation, thermal insulation, lightweight, low emission, etc.
- 3D Formable → different binder can be used.
- Application: Transportation Vehicles (cars, trains, buses, trucks and aircraft), protective workwear, filtration, construction and other various industrial applications (insulation of pipes, core material for VIP's, etc.).

Table 2: smartMELAMINE:

Application	fineness [µm]	Weight [g/m ²]	Acoustic insulation	Thermal insulation	Lightweight	Filtration efficiency	Heat/Fire resistance	Chemical resistance
Mobility (bus, car, plane, ship)	5-20	100-600	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
Filtration	0.5-10	20-200				✓	✓	✓
Thermal Protective Clothing	10-20	20-200		✓	✓		✓	✓
Industrial Applications	5-20	50-600	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓

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FOR FURTHER INFORMATION

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